

**Tail-first ingestion of a Sharptooth Catfish *Clarias gariepinus* (Siluriformes: Clariidae)
by a Dusky-bellied Water Snake *Lycodonorphus laevis* (Squamata: Lamprophiidae)
in South Africa**

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ABSTRACT

We report here on a filmed observation of a Dusky-bellied Water Snake *Lycodonorphus laevis* (Günther, 1862) preying on a Sharptooth Catfish *Clarias gariepinus* (Burchell, 1822) in the Umgeni River near the town of Howick in KwaZulu-Natal Province, South Africa. This represents the first published record of any non-cichlid fish in the diet of *L. laevis*, and apparently also the first case of tail-first ingestion of prey by any species of *Lycodonorphus* Fitzinger, 1843 in its natural habitat.

KEYWORDS: *Clarias gariepinus*, Clariidae, Sharptooth Catfish, *Lycodonorphus laevis*, Lamprophiidae, Dusky-bellied Water Snake, behaviour, predation, South Africa.

INTRODUCTION

The ‘water snake’ genus *Lycodonorphus* Fitzinger, 1843 occurs in the southern half of Africa. Seven species are currently recognised in the genus, since three species have recently been transferred to other genera, i.e., *Boaedon subtaeniatus* (Laurent, 1954), *B. upembae* (Laurent, 1954) and *Elaiophis inornatus* (Duméril, Bibron & Duméril, 1854) (Greenbaum *et al.* 2015; Keates *et al.* 2022; Trape 2023; Tiutenko *et al.* 2025). The seven species are semi-aquatic (e.g., *L. rufulus* (Lichtenstein, 1823)) or largely aquatic (e.g., *L. bicolor* (Günther, 1894), *L. laevis* (Günther, 1862)) and, in nature, feed only on frogs (sometimes also tadpoles) and/or fish. *Lycodonorphus bicolor* is reportedly a fish specialist, preying mainly on cichlids but occasionally also dorosomatids (Loveridge 1958; Madsen & Osterkamp 1982), whereas in natural conditions two species have been recorded feeding only on frogs: *L. whytii* (Boulenger, 1897), which is known to feed on *Amietia* sp. (also tadpoles in captivity); and *L. obscuriventris* FitzSimons, 1964, which feeds on species of *Kassina*, *Pyxicephalus* and *Phrynobatrachus* (also *Ptychadena* and various tadpoles in captivity) (Loveridge 1958; Broadley 1990; Kyle *et al.* 2021; Pietersen *et al.* 2023). The other four species of *Lycodonorphus* are known to eat

both fish and frogs. For example, *L. leleupi* (Laurent, 1950) preys on the fish *Barbus* and *Kneria*, and shovel-nosed frogs (*Hemisus*); *L. mlanjensis* Loveridge, 1953 preys on the Sharptooth Catfish *Clarias gariepinus* (Burchell, 1822) and ranid tadpoles (also small fish, and frogs such as *Xenopus laevis*, in captivity) (Loveridge 1958; Broadley 1966); and *L. rufulus* (Lichtenstein, 1823) feeds on fish (including barbel and carp in captivity), frogs (e.g. *Amietia* sp., *Arthroleptis xenodactyloides*, *Hyperolius tuberilinguis*, *Strongylopus rhodesianus*, *Xenopus laevis*) and tadpoles (Loveridge 1958; FitzSimons 1962; Broadley 1966).

The Dusky-bellied Water Snake *Lycodonorphus laevis* occurs in the eastern parts of South Africa, mainly in the provinces of Mpumalanga, KwaZulu-Natal and Eastern Cape, and in Eswatini (Bates *et al.* 2014). These snakes are fairly large aquatic constrictors, and according to Haagner and Branch (1994), the largest female measured 1315 mm (1085 mm snout-vent length + 230 mm tail length) and the largest male was 988 mm (751 + 237). They are often seen swimming underwater in streams and rivers (Raw 1973; Marais 2004). Although the latter authors noted that this snake, which has round pupils typical of diurnal snakes, is often active by day, and a few photographs are available of it feeding by day

in nature (Predation records 2025), Rabięga (2018: 61) stated that it is “largely nocturnal both in the wild and captivity”. *Lycodonomorphus laevis* is a very water-dependent snake and will dehydrate and perish, reportedly within two days, if precluded from immersing in water (Raw 1973; Rabięga 2018).

We report here on a filmed observation of a *L. laevis* preying on a catfish *C. gariepinus* in the wild in South Africa.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

On 6 October 2024, around midday, an adult *Lycodonomorphus laevis* was observed in the Umgeni River in Hilton College Nature Reserve (29.46691° S, 30.28777° E; 731 m a.s.l.), below the town of Howick in KwaZulu-Natal Province, South Africa. The snake was filmed by Mr Neil Goss (pers. comm., October 2024; see [Supplementary video](#)) as it floated downstream in shallow, clear, gently-flowing water with large stones at the bottom, with what appeared to be two coils wrapped around a catfish (*Clarias gariepinus*), which had its head and whiskers protruding from the snake’s mouth. The snake was easily identifiable by its plain grey-brown upperparts, and pale yellow underparts decorated with brown blotches, those at mid-venter forming a broken stripe; whereas the catfish was recognisable by the brown of its upper head, pinkish-white underparts and 3–4 pairs of long barbels visible on the mouth (Fig. 1). After the video footage ended, the snake was observed by Mr N. Goss (pers. comm., October 2024 & January 2025) as it swam to the banks of the river where it completed the process of swallowing the fish.

Figure 1: Dusky-bellied Water Snake (*Lycodonomorphus laevis*) swallowing a Sharptooth Catfish (*Clarias gariepinus*) tail-first. Locality: Umgeni River near the town of Howick, KwaZulu-Natal Province, South Africa. (Photo: Neil Goss)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This article represents the first report of a non-cichlid fish in the diet of *Lycodonomorphus laevis*. Also, apart from this new record, the only other congener that has been recorded feeding on *Clarias gariepinus* (or any other catfish) in nature is *L. mlanjensis*, as mentioned above. It should, however, be noted that a catfish (*Clarias* sp.) was recovered from the stomach of a ‘house snake’ *Boaedon upembae*, until recently regarded as a subspecies of *L. subtaeniatus* (Greenbaum *et al.* 2015). Another genus of African water snakes is *Grayia* Günther, 1858, which contains five species. These snakes, found in the central, western and eastern parts of the continent, also prey primarily on fish and/or frogs (sometimes including tadpoles), and at least two species—*Grayia ornata* (Bocage, 1866) and *G. obscura* Chaney, Greenbaum & Pauwels, 2024—include catfish (Clariidae) in their diets (Pauwels *et al.* 2000; Chaney *et al.* 2024).

Perhaps the earliest comments about the diet of *L. laevis* are those of Isemonger (1955: 67) who noted that three snakes collected by him were “studied for several months” and “ate well in captivity, preferring lizards to frogs”. FitzSimons (1962: 105) noted that *L. laevis* fed “mainly on frogs”. Raw (1973: 717) recorded frogs, tadpoles (*Amietia*, *Phrynobatrachus*) and fish (‘*Tilapia*’, Cichlidae) in its diet and noted that large prey are constricted but smaller prey “merely seized and rapidly swallowed while still struggling”. Regarding the ‘*Tilapia*’ mentioned above, Mr L.R.G. Raw had captured a young *L. laevis* and a few small cichlids, and when placed on the banks of the river, the snake fed on at least two of these fish (about 2–3 cm long); whereas the frogs and tadpoles were observed (by Mr Ray Parker) being eaten in captivity (L.R.G. Raw pers. comm., December 2024 & January 2025). Prey captured underwater is swallowed without the need to surface for air, unless the process is prolonged, in which case the prey is dragged to the surface to finish it off (R. Parker pers. comm. to Raw 1973).

In their review of *L. laevis*, Haagner and Branch (1994) found cichlid fish (*Pseudocrenilabris philander*, eaten by two snakes), frogs (only a fully aquatic Common Clawed Frog *Xenopus laevis* could be identified to the species level) and tadpoles in the stomachs of museum specimens, and also mentioned (with reference to ‘Carpenter pers. comm.’) that captive snakes fed on the frogs *Ptychadena*, *Tomopterna* and *Amietia*. Rabięga (2018) reported on specimens from an isolated population of *L. laevis* from central South Africa (Free State/Gauteng border) and noted that captive snakes of this species fed on the adult frogs *Amietia delalandii* and *A. poyntoni*, tadpoles of *Pyxicephalus adspersus*, and the cichlid fish *Tilapia sparrmanii*. Maritz and Maritz (2020) later recorded the Mozambique *Tilapia* (*Oreochromis*

mis mossambicus) and Common River Frog (*Amietia delalandii*) in the diet of *L. laevis* in the wild based on photographic evidence (Predation records 2025). However, the snake shown eating the *Amietia* is in fact a *Lycodonomorphus rufulus* (plain, salmon-coloured belly). There are also additional photographic records showing specimens of *L. laevis* grasping or swallowing prey (Predation records 2025, images saved), namely an unidentified fish, and a *X. laevis* adult, which was reportedly regurgitated after capture and which was still alive (Baldwin 2025).

Regarding other potential prey, although Isemonger (1955) stated that captive *L. laevis* preferred lizards to frogs, Rabiega (2018) noted that his captive snakes refused to feed on scincid lizards (*Trachylepis*) as well as rodents. Rabiega (2018) also mentioned that a captive snake that was offered a sand frog (*Tomopterna tandyi*) bit it on the head and attempted to swallow it without constricting it first, and after repeating this behaviour several times, the frog was disregarded.

Snakes usually swallow their prey head-first as this allows for easier passage into the gut, taking advantage of the natural ‘folding back’ of limbs, sharp fins, spines and quills which might otherwise stick in the throat or tear the gastro-intestinal tract (e.g. FitzSimons 1962; Mori 2006; photo records in Predation records 2025). While the feeding event reported on here appears to be the only known record of any species of *Lycodonomorphus* swallowing prey tail-first, this situation may be common when prey is small, especially in the case of frogs and tadpoles that have fairly flexible legs (or no legs in young tadpoles) and lack spiny body parts that may impede swallowing. Mori (2006) reported that several snake species do not rely on head-first ingestion of anuran prey, and some such as the anurophagous snake *Rhabdophis tigrinus* (Boie, 1826), often align the two legs of the frog and then swallow them together from the tips, resulting in similar resistance to when prey is swallowed head-first. Prey-handling behaviour has not been studied in detail for most African snake species and presents a potentially interesting field of investigation.

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Supplementary video: An adult *Lycodonomorphus laevis* floating in gently-flowing water with two coils wrapped around a catfish *Clarias gariepinus* (10.5281/zenodo.16095730).

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